

DERIVATIVES OF PHOSPHANILIC ACID

BY N. S. LIMAYE AND B. V. BHIDE

Several derivatives phosphanilic acid have been prepared

The present paper describes the synthesis of several derivatives of phosphanilic acid which resemble the derivatives of arsanilic acid and sulphanilamide possessing equivalent or greater activity than that of the parent compound.

Phosphanilic acid (required for the purpose) was prepared following essentially the method of Bauer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63** 2137). *p*-Bromophenylphosphinic acid (Davies and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 276) was used instead of *p*-chlorophenylphosphinic acid as in the method of Bauer (*loc cit.*). The advantage of using *p*-bromophenylphosphinic acid is that the reaction with ammonia need not be carried out under pressure. It also gives better yields and hence is more suitable for the preparation of large quantities of phosphanilic acid.

Acetyl, butyryl, caproyl and succinyl derivatives of phosphanilic acid were prepared by shaking a solution of the acid in sodium bicarbonate with the appropriate anhydride, as the corresponding acid chlorides failed to react in the presence of pyridine. Benzoyl chloride however, readily gave the benzoyl derivative. Chloroacetyl chloride on heating with phosphanilic acid gave a product which was decomposed by water and hence could not be identified.

Phosphanilic acid was diazotised and coupled with resorcinol, pyrrole and *m*-phenylenediamine when the corresponding azo dyes were obtained.

Preparation of carbamidophosphanilic acid could not be carried out by heating with potassium cyanate or cyanogen bromide. The ammonium salt of the compound, however, was obtained by heating urea with phosphanilic acid.

Attempts were made to prepare phosphanilamide, the analogue of sulphanilamide. *p*-Bromophenylphosphinyl amide (prepared from *p*-bromophenylphosphonyl oxychloride, $\text{BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{POCl}_2$, and ammonia) gave the amide in low yield by heating with aqueous ammonia in presence of cuprous oxide. Similar attempts to prepare the analogue of sulphathiazole failed.

The diethylamine and ethanolamine salts of phosphanilic acid were prepared by treating the acid with the appropriate amine, followed by crystallisation from water. The salts contain two equivalents of the base for one molecule of the acid, as shown by the analysis.

Benzaldehyde did not react with phosphanilic acid on heating without a solvent or in alcoholic solution, but gave the anil in a low yield when heated in the presence

of anhydrous zinc chloride. However, the anil was unstable and could not be obtained pure.

The antibacterial properties of these compounds have been already reported (Bhide and Kanitkar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, **16**, 223). None of these derivatives has been found to be superior to phosphanilic acid in antibacterial properties.

Phosphanilic acid has been found to inhibit completely the growth of *M. tuberculosis in vitro* in a concentration of 1:5000. Preliminary pharmacological tests show that phosphanilic acid is comparatively non-toxic to laboratory animals and is little absorbed in the blood (unpublished work).

EXPERIMENTAL

Phosphanilic Acid.—*p*-Bromophenylphosphinic acid (6 g.), freshly prepared cuprous oxide (4.5 g.) and ammonia (d 0.88, 100 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath till all the cuprous oxide dissolved (10 hours). On removal of the copper as copper sulphide by passing H_2S , the solution was made acidic to Congo red, when a granular precipitate of phosphanilic acid was obtained. On purifying according to Bauer it melted at 245°.

The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives of phosphanilic acid were prepared by treating a solution of the acid in sodium bicarbonate with acetic anhydride and benzoyl chloride respectively. The acetyl derivative had m. p. 229° (cf. Bauer, *loc. cit.*).

Benzoyl derivative was purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate and precipitating with acid, m. p. 287°. It is insoluble in the usual organic solvents and is sparingly soluble in acetone. (Found: N, 5.23; $C_{13}H_{12}O_4NP$ requires N, 5.05 per cent).

Succinylphosphanilic Acid.—Phosphanilic acid (1 g.), dissolved in the minimum quantity of sodium bicarbonate, was shaken with succinic anhydride (2 g.) till the solution did not give the test for a primary amine with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. The solution on acidification to Congo red with hydrochloric acid was evaporated to dryness. The residue was Soxhleted with ether to remove free succinic acid. The residue, easily soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents, on recrystallisation from water melted at 276°. (Found: N, 5.36; equiv., 93. $C_{10}H_{12}O_6NP$ requires N, 5.13 per cent. Equiv., 91).

Butyrylphosphanilic acid is insoluble in water and in the common organic solvents, m. p. 284°. (Found: N, 5.81. $C_{10}H_{14}O_4NP$ requires N, 5.76 per cent)

Caproylphosphanilic acid crystallises from dioxan, m. p. 204°. (Found: N, 5.36. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4NP$ requires N, 5.16 per cent).

Azo dyes from Phosphanilic Acid.—To phosphanilic acid (1 g.) in 5N-HCl (2 c.c.) sodium nitrite (0.4 g.) was added, followed by resorcinol (0.63 g.), dissolved in sodium hydroxide, keeping the temperature at 0°. A red dye was obtained, melting at 211°. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_2P$ requires N, 9.52 per cent).

An azo dye, violet in colour and without any definite melting point, was obtained from pyrrole and phosphanilic acid in an analogous manner. (Found: N, 16.63. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2P$ requires N, 16.73 per cent).

m-Phenylenediamine gave a red dye having no definite melting point (Found: N, 18.87. $C_{12}H_{13}O_8N_4P$ requires N, 19.18 per cent).

Ammonium salt of Carbamidophosphanilic Acid.—Phosphanilic acid (i.e.) and urea (0.6 g) were heated at 120° for 6 hours. The resulting product was extracted with alcohol to remove urea. The residue was dissolved in water with the addition of dilute ammonia and evaporated to dryness. The resulting solid did not give a test for a free primary amino group. It does not melt up to 300° . The nitrogen content and the absence of a primary amino group indicate that the compound is, in all probability, the ammonium salt of carbamidophosphanilic acid. (Found: N, 17.92. $C_7H_{12}O_4N_3P$ requires N, 18.03 per cent).

Amide of Phosphanilic Acid.—*p*-Bromophenylphosphonyl chloride was treated with ice-cold concentrated ammonia. A white precipitate of the diamide of *p*-bromophenylphosphinic acid slowly separated. The precipitate was filtered and washed with water. It crystallised from alcohol in plates and melted to a turbid liquid at 202° which became clear at 256° . (Found: N, 12.11. $C_6H_6OBrN_2P$ requires N, 11.91 per cent).

The above amide (8 g.) and freshly prepared cuprous oxide (8 g.) were heated on the water-bath with ammonia (*d* 0.88, 150 c.c.) till all the cuprous oxide dissolved. It was then acidified, copper removed as sulphide, and the solution treated with sodium bicarbonate till the solution was slightly acidic to Congo red, when a white precipitate settled down. It was purified by dissolving it in acid, treating with animal charcoal and precipitating with bicarbonate solution. It was then obtained in a snow white form, *m. p.* 224° . A little over two equivalents of ammonia were evolved on heating it with sodium hydroxide. It did not analyse satisfactorily for nitrogen by Dumas method. It was, in all probability, the diamide, as it was insoluble in bicarbonate solution and gave all the tests for a free primary amino group. [Found: N (as ammonia), 17.5. $C_6H_{10}ON_4P$ requires N 16.38 per cent].

Reaction of 2-Aminothiazole with p-Bromophenylphosphonyl Chloride.—*p*-Bromophenylphosphonyl chloride (27 g.) and 2-aminothiazole (22 g.) were mixed in dry benzene with cooling. After allowing it to stand overnight it was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. On removal of benzene, a black residue was obtained which was treated with sodium carbonate. It was boiled and filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling gave a brown solid. On treating it with animal charcoal it crystallised from water, *m. p.* 187° .

The free acid was obtained from the above sodium salt by dissolving in the minimum quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid and on addition of absolute alcohol followed by ether. It melts at 225° . It is soluble in water and alcohol but insoluble in ether. (Found: N, 8.93. $C_9H_8O_2BrN_2PS$ requires N, 8.78 per cent).

The acid gave a picrate, *m. p.* 232° . (Found: N, 12.58. $C_{13}H_{11}O_8BrN_3PS$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

Diethylamine Salt of Phosphanilic Acid.—Phosphanilic acid (1 g.) was suspended in water and diethylamine (1 c.c.) was added to it. It was warmed on the water-bath for half an hour. The diethylamine salt slowly crystallised from water in needles melting at 212°. (Found : N, 12.96. $C_{11}H_{20}O_3N_2P$ requires N, 13.16 per cent).

Ethanolamine salt was prepared in a similar manner and crystallised in plates from water m. p. 178°. (Found : N, 13.97. $C_{10}H_{22}O_3N_2P$ requires N, 14.24 per cent).

MAHARAJA PRATAPSINH CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SIR PARASHURAMBRAU COLLEGE, POONA.

Received March 16, 1948.